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Application of Digital Twins for Low Carbon Development and Resilience: A Comparative Analysis of Smart City Evolution in New Delhi, New York and London

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Abstract: This paper examines the application of Digital Twin (DT) technology in three major urban contexts—New Delhi, New York City, and London—highlighting their diverse pathways of adoption and unique governance challenges. DTs, distinguished from static models by their dynamic data integration and two-way communication, are increasingly employed as urban management tools. Beyond these case studies, the paper engages with the concept of *deep sustainability*, questioning whether DTs can contribute to systemic transformations rather than incremental efficiency gains. While DTs hold promise for simulating policy interventions, reducing environmental harms, and fostering transparency, challenges of cost, trust, and the risk of remaining mere “digital shadows” persist. Overall, this comparative study highlights both the opportunities as well as limitations of DTs as tools for advancing equitable and sustainable urban governance.

Keywords: Applications of Digital Twins, Deep Sustainability, Internet of Things

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Main highlights:

1. Examples from Europe highlight the versatility of DT as a tool.
2. Easily monitorable public services are conducive to digital twinning.
3. Open data and sensor networks are a prerequisite.
4. A transparent and responsible governance is essential for ethical use of DT.

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Introduction

The term “Digital Twin” broadly refers to virtual replicas of physical entities or even social structures, purposed to serve as testbeds for a wide range of innovations and interventions before they are implemented in the real world. It is crucial to distinguish a Digital Twin from a static econometric model because the former is constantly attempting to simulate 1:1 its physical counterpart, whereas the latter requires manual updating to remain relevant. This is achieved through a two-way data flow between the physical entity and its digital replica which is largely automated. In some contexts, the mere active simulation of a physical entity is classified as a “Digital Shadow,” and a flow of commands or intervention back to the physical counterpart is necessary to qualify as a Digital Twin.

Literature Review and Applications in UK/ Europe

Digital Twins (DTs) are experiencing robust application and innovation in infrastructure development and management across Western countries, especially in the United Kingdom.

For example, the UK architecture firm Building Design Partnership (BDP) employed an Unreal Engine-based 3D model to guide a major restoration of the Parliament. This model not only facilitated visualization of the existing structure but also enabled the simulation of potential expansions, such as additional rooms and halls. There are plans to digitize individual assets like statues and paintings, allowing architects and designers enhanced flexibility in planning and conservation. Complementing this approach, NavLive, another UK firm, utilizes LiDAR-based technologies to create detailed digital records of physical environments.

A noteworthy initiative in this domain is the creation of the CAMHighways dataset by the Digital Roads Team at Cambridge University. This dataset was developed to streamline the construction and management of digital twins for all UK highways. By doing so, the initiative

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aims to automate highway inspection and maintenance processes with the help of virtual reality, robotic simulations, and AI-driven data analyses.

Beyond structural management, the United Kingdom has demonstrated leadership in integrating digital twin technology with issues of climate change, sustainability, and urban planning. At COP26 in 2021, the UK introduced CReDo (Climate Resilience Demonstrator), the nation's first climate-resilience digital twin system. CReDo was purpose-built to mitigate the impacts of flooding, particularly on mobile network performance and the delivery of essential utilities such as water. Its long-term vision involves serving as a model for climate change mitigation and for progressing toward net-zero targets. What makes CReDo distinctive is its strategy of fostering an "ecosystem of connected digital twins," which suggests that independent yet compatible digital replicas could eventually cooperate, functioning as a "super-twin" by combining their individual data and analytical power.

The UK has furthered the integration of DTs across various regions and use cases:

- In Cambridge, a city-scale digital twin is used to simulate scenarios such as electric vehicle (EV) adoption, merging socio-technical perspectives with urban analytics.
- In Lancaster, a non-metropolitan area with an urban-rural mix, a City Information Model serves as a precursor for urban digital twin development, addressing the unique needs of diverse landscapes such as coastal towns and forests.
- In London, the UCL Here East Campus uses a DT with IoT sensors for two-way communication, enhancing operational management and stakeholder engagement via mixed realities.

Looking beyond the UK, Germany provides an excellent example of comprehensive digital twin application in the town of Herrenberg near Stuttgart. Their DT encompasses detailed 3D

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modeling of the built environment, simulation of street networks, urban mobility, air-flow, and pollution, alongside qualitative and quantitative data on pedestrian and cyclist routes.

Residents actively contributed to the project by using their smartphones as mobility trackers, and proposed interventions could be virtually visualized and evaluated by the community.

Collectively, these cases highlight the versatility and potential of digital twins in transforming how infrastructure, urban planning, and environmental sustainability challenges are addressed across both the UK and Europe.

Existing Applications in India

Though DT technology has not witnessed the same level of proliferation in India and the initial adoption has been limited to the private sector (customer facing services nonetheless), the ambitions to integrate it into governance is very much thriving. SANGAM is India's version of National Digital Twin Programme (NDTP) launched by the Department of Telecommunications in February 2024. The common aim is government led capacity building in the twinning sector but divergence is seen in the focus on forming frameworks in which the NDTP has been much more ambitious.

GMR Airports integrated DT technology named Airport Predictive Operation Centre (APOC) at the Rajiv Gandhi International Airport in Hyderabad in December last year. The APOC integrates airside, landside, and terminal operations into a unified system. Major international airports across the EU, UK and USA have already long-implemented APOCs with varying degrees of integration. In Delhi, the IGI airport recorded a landmark in 2023 by being the first airport globally to implement 1000 taxibots which are designed to transport aircraft to and from the ramp to the runway. Deep implementation of APOC at the Indira Gandhi

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International Airport (10th busiest airport in the world) must be expedited to further the reduction in aviation related emissions.

“Airports with APOCs consistently report significant benefits, including improved operational performance, enhanced passenger experience and cost savings. They also emphasise that APOCs are continually evolving, with systems and data playing a central role. However, the most significant challenge in APOC implementation is driving a cultural shift. Early involvement of all stakeholders, fostering transparency, and clearly defining roles and responsibilities are vital to the successful launch and operation of an APOC.” (Eurocontrol, Airport Operations Centres Performance Study 2025)

New Delhi

As of 2025, more than 34 million people inhabit the National Capital Territory (NCT) which comprises the capital city of Delhi and its surrounding administrative boundary. It ranks 11th globally in population density and 2nd in terms of absolute population after Tokyo. With so many inhabitants to cater to, challenges in efficient public service delivery are abundant particularly when these challenges need to be tackled within the constraints of sustainability and low-carbon development.

Potential Application of Digital Twin Technology in New Delhi

New Delhi does not have the benefit of tier 2 and tier 3 cities which can build integrated infrastructure from the ground up - because most major transport infrastructure is already part of the built-environment. That said, it can be used for the following areas relating to sustainability:

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Despite occupying only 0.045% of the country's total land area, Delhi contributes an entire percent to the national annual CO₂ stock, where 61% of the emissions come from the stationary combustion (power generation) sector (Arora et. al. 2023). DT technology can be utilized to map the existing unbuilt environment to supplement installing green (carbon) sinks in the city, which can help absorb some of this carbon, furthering India's national ambitions to create an additional carbon sink of 2.5 to 3 billion tonnes of CO₂e by 2030.

To deal with the congestion resulting from the YoY growth in personal 4W traffic, there is scope to implement a traffic management system (inspired by Bengaluru model) based on real time monitoring of congestion through camera systems. The algorithm outputs optimum traffic light patterns across the monitored area. This can achieve significant reduction in particulate matter (PM) emissions from idling in traffic. In the private sector, there is potential for contractors/builders to use sensor-based technology in not only construction but also monitoring of drainage faults – which are prevalent in many high rise high end skyscraper complexes in Gurugram.

When communicating the potential of new technologies to policymakers, there is a justified emphasis on the cost-benefit calculation of investing in its adoption because of the high initial cost of integration with existing systems.

Potential Application in the Public Sector

There is a massive potential for application of Digital Twin technology in the Public Distribution System - the disbursement responsibility of ration falls upon the state government. Digital twinning technology can help digitize distribution and allotment using a real-time inventory management system (tap in to receive endowment). Overall costs can be minimized if the twin is transparent and problems are easy to debug/diagnose (more technical

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the model = more the premium that can be charged by a private partner for maintenance and support).

Emerging smart infrastructure is capable of “communicating” both internally and externally, adapting to real-time conditions, and reorganizing itself in response to usage patterns and environmental shifts. Policy measures such as extended producer responsibility (EPR), carbon pricing, and green public procurement (as seen in the EU, Japan, and the Netherlands) are also accelerating the transition to circular procurement approaches. The built environment plays a major role in global energy consumption and emissions, accounting for roughly 37% of CO₂ emissions linked to energy, considering both operational and embodied energy (GlobalABC & UNEP, 2022). In India, energy demand from this sector is projected to increase eightfold by 2047, fueled by rapid urbanization, economic progress, and rising living standards (NITI Aayog & IEA, 2015). Furthermore, since more than 70% of the building stock projected for 2040 has yet to be constructed, India faces a vital opportunity to incorporate low-carbon, climate-resilient strategies into new developments (BEE, 2019).

Challenges Which Need to Be Overcome in Public Sector Adoption

The key challenge will be balancing the cost of building new infrastructure (since government tenders put a high weightage on low cost of construction) and sustainable construction. (Any CBA should factor in the cost of greening existing infrastructure vs cost of creating green infra from ground up). Moreover, appropriate frameworks and policy objectives will be required as are present in the EU to inspire confidence among industry and the public (if tax revenue is being used to subsidize green construction).

In mega-cities like New Delhi or London where the potential for digital integration is high, digital twins that are open-source or publicly monitorable can enhance accountability within

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the bureaucracy. However, it must be noted that this would require the dissolution of vested interests held by those in positions of authority. From a political perspective, transparency is in the interest of the governing party – especially when considerable investment of resources is directed towards development. Unlike conventional computer modelling which is static in nature and relies on primary data-collection, sensor-based modelling is dynamic and thus data shortage no longer remains a limiting factor. Priority sectors for adoption should be ranked based on the number of people currently affected by inefficiency and potential for enhancing efficiency and widening welfare delivery.

What is important to note, is that all factors that inhibit a more transparent, technology-intensive mode of governance also inhibit equitable socioeconomic development more broadly. Though it may require significant restructuring of current incentives (scope for nudge theory) among the bureaucracy and the citizenry, the gains from the adoption of twinning and sensor-integration in general are expected to be exponentially more equitable and just relative to the gains generated within the existing system of governance. Thus, perhaps the only necessary condition for expediting the adoption of technologies like Digital Twinning and IoT is a responsible government which is serious about fostering sustained sustainability.

New York City

Smart City and Digital Twin Implementation

New York City (NYC) stands as a global exemplar in leveraging smart city technologies to drive sustainability, public service efficiency, and digital equity. The city's initiatives are

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rooted in a robust information and communication technology (ICT) framework, powered by public-private partnerships and data-driven governance models. At the forefront is LinkNYC, a high-visibility smart infrastructure project providing public Wi-Fi across the five boroughs. More recently, NYC has begun to explore the integration of digital twin technology to advance its smart service capabilities.

Smart Service City and LinkNYC

LinkNYC is NYC's flagship public broadband initiative, replacing payphones with interactive kiosks offering free high-speed internet, phone calls, and digital city service access. Built at no taxpayer cost and funded through advertising revenue, LinkNYC is a cornerstone of NYC's digital inclusion strategy. It also serves as foundational infrastructure for collecting urban data essential to smart city applications. Alongside LinkNYC, city departments like DoITT and NYCCTO manage programs that span broadband expansion, IoT deployment, and open data systems. These efforts enable NYC to function as a Smart Service City, one that uses data to deliver services in real time, from adaptive traffic signals and smart meters to environmental monitoring and emergency response.

Integrating Digital Twins into NYC's Smart City Framework

While NYC's use of digital twins is still emerging, the foundation has been laid through interconnected infrastructure and sensor networks. NYC's Internet of Things (IoT) strategy and Open Data platforms enable the real-time data integration necessary for digital twins. For example, real-time traffic, air quality, water usage, and energy consumption data can be

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synthesized into digital replicas of the city. These models support predictive maintenance, disaster planning, and urban design simulations.

The Mayor's Office of the CTO has published IoT guidelines (G-IoT) and the Internet Master Plan to support responsible deployment of connected devices, paving the way for robust digital twin development. Additionally, platforms like the NYC Open Data Portal already provide structured data that could be used to power twin environments for public safety, mobility, and resource management.

Looking Ahead

As NYC advances toward its OneNYC 2050 goals of sustainability, equity, and resilience, digital twins are expected to become a key tool. They can help city officials simulate policies before implementation, model energy efficiency upgrades, and plan for extreme weather events with greater precision. By integrating digital twins with its existing smart infrastructure—particularly through projects like LinkNYC and the IoT network—NYC is creating a blueprint for future-ready cities. New York City's smart city ecosystem, centered around ICT initiatives such as LinkNYC, is increasingly capable of supporting advanced technologies like digital twins. By merging real-time data with spatial simulations, the city is poised to elevate its capacity for sustainable planning, responsive governance, and improved urban living.

Digital Twins for Deep Sustainability – A Critical Analysis

The notion of deep sustainability is based in the premise that the mere substitution by renewable for non-renewable resources is insufficient. Nor is enhancing process efficiency viable for achieving *sustainable sustainability*. Broadly defined, deep sustainability is a

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school of thought that proposes a radical rethink of our economic systems, with an emphasis on the ethical and ontological questions associated with sustainability. For example, instead of restricting discourse to preventing temperature rise above 1.5°C or achieving net zero, it would also give precedence to the disproportionate effects of runaway global warming and climate change on the financially impoverished. Moreover, it distinguishes itself from *shallow sustainability* or *anthropocentrism* – both of which put human material interests (disguised as commerce) at the forefront of any policymaking by questioning the extractive nature of the capitalist mode of production and its effects on other species (Ikerd, 2014). It also questions whether the 17 SDGs are accomplishable within the current hyper-consumerist economy (Martin, 2022).

To recap, deep sustainability calls for amendments at the societal and institutional level because it holds the view that the very nature of anthropocentric consumerism and greed is the anti-thesis of true sustainability. To assess the application of DTs in facilitating deep sustainability, it is first important to remind ourselves that DTs are purpose built. Beyond digitization and simplifying operations, they utilize their excellent mimicry of their physical partner asset to serve as testbeds for interventions. Using Internet-of-Things (IoT) integration, dynamic and unpredictable challenges like water supply pipe leakages and electricity disruption can be foreseen and rectified before they occur. These can significantly reduce the usage of highly polluting diesel generators which are operated during power cuts in summer months and water tankers which also run on diesel. Such innovations are already in effect in cities like Singapore, Seoul, Tokyo and Chicago. DTs can also be used to redevelop slums in parts rather than resorting to displacement to facilitate construction.

The most recognizable and apparent obstacle hindering adoption of sensor-based utility management is the unorganized nature of service provision. For example, a slum in New

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Delhi may not have a piped water supply from the municipality because it is considered “illegal settlement.” Even when piped water supply is present, it may not be adequately reliable and the slum residents may well be accessing water from a community-constructed borewell. Further, vested interests and insufficient manpower at the executory level may inhibit enthusiasm towards any technology-intensive solutions which may require considerable training/time. Similarly, many housing colonies in New Delhi remain “unregularized” meaning that they do not have municipal water supply despite. While some residents are in favour of regularization because they foresee a jump in their property valuation once regularization occurs but others fear it will bring about rampant construction, noise pollution and congestion. In sum, adoption of DT technology can be restricted by three I’s— infrastructure gaps, institutional weaknesses, and incentive incompatibility.

Literature confirms this by assessing *industrial modernity* across various geographically diverse countries, finding that structural changes promoting deep sustainability broadly fit into three sometimes overlapping reasons: practices (fossil fuel based economy/orientation of R&D largely indifferent to sustainability), ideas (instrumental view of nature), and institutions (regulatory ecosystem with relatively weak reaching environmental protection/prioritization of societal over environmental concerns) (Pahker et. al, 2024).

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Figure 1: Obstacles to Deep Sustainability [Pahker et. al. 2024]

In mega-cities like New Delhi or London where the potential for digital integration is high, digital twins that are open-source or publicly monitorable can enhance accountability within the bureaucracy. However, it must be noted that this would require the dissolution of vested interests held by those in positions of authority. From a political perspective, transparency is in the interest of the governing party – especially when considerable investment of resources is directed towards development. Unlike conventional computer modelling which is static in nature and relies on primary data-collection, sensor-based modelling is dynamic and thus data shortage no longer remains a limiting factor.

Limitations

Ethical Concerns and a trust deficit surrounding digital twins are already documented in literature. The use of DT technology by governments and policy makers is limited by the reliance on automated sensor-based feedback loops. Put simply, DTs in their current nascency cannot be used in domains where the observable of interest is not captured continuously or where interventions cannot flow digitally. For example, easily monitorable and centrally

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controllable public utilities like water, electricity, public transport and traffic systems are conducive to digital twinning. However, social issues with ethical/accountability dimensions which cannot be digitally abstracted cannot be captured by DTs, for example property rights or inequality.

Moreover, it is useful to be mindful of the distinction between digital twins and digital shadows because most of the existing prototypes discussed/developed thus far (particularly in the climate and sustainability sector) fall into the latter category. This is by virtue of such prototypes lacking a “*user-to-asset*” communication channel i.e., the ability of the user to pass instruction/information to the real-world asset.

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